

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IMPULSE BUYING BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses in understanding the factors influencing the impulse buying behavior among young women. In this study a survey was conducted among women between the age group of 18 to 25 years. The study is based on primary data collected through questionnaires and also secondary data collected from books journals and the internet. Impulsive buying behavior is better understood by examining the impulsive buying tendency that shapes such behaviors. Due to globalization the younger generations now have easy access in purchasing a wide variety of goods or products. Apart from this there are wide varieties of psychological/social as well as marketing factors that pushes impulsive buying.

Hence this study is made to find out more regarding such factors that pushes young women into impulsive buying.

Keywords: impulse buying, buying behaviors, women buyers, psychological factors

INTRODUCTION

An impulse purchase or impulse buy is an unplanned decision to buy a product or service made just before taking a buying decision. The one who makes purchase is called as an impulse buyer or the impulse researcher. Research findings have concluded that emotions and feelings play a huge role in purchasing and is triggered by seeing the product or at times at the exposure to a well-crafted promotional message. Impulse buying disturbs the regular buying pattern or the normal buying decision. The regular or logical sequence of the consumer's action is replaced with an irrational moment of self-gratification. Impulse items appeal to the emotional side of consumers. Preventing impulsive buying involves techniques such as setting budgets before shopping and taking time to make any purchase decision. If in case of purchasing automobiles or home appliances, are considered as an emotional purchase. Automobiles in most of the cases are emotional purchase rather than rational ones.

The multiplex malls hypermarkets and online shops or markets are the modern retailing environment they have been developed as one of the major growing industry with several domestic and international players entering into the market. The major objective of this study is to understand the factors that pushes into impulsive buying.

LITURATURE REVIEW

Kacen & Lee (2002) Concluded that age is an important factor to be considered in case of impulsive behavior as they feel less risky to spend money. Impulsive buying is higher between the age of 18-39 years of age.

Priyanka & Robbie (2012) Concluded that individuals with different genders tend to have different buying behavior so women are apt to impulsive buying more than men.

Wells et al (2007) Concluded that impulsive buying behavior highly depends upon the income level of the family individual or their monthly allowance.

Block and Morwitz (1999) Concluded that impulsive buying is an item with no deliberation after the result of powerful urge.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study all the factors that influences impulsive buying behavior in women aged between 18-25 years.
- To examine the effect of the different variables of impulsive buying.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- This study is based on the information of the representation sample group selected from a total population of a smaller lot of people hence; it does not cover the factors influencing impulsive buying behavior of the entire city or town but only a part of it.
- The analysis was conducted through questionnaire hence, there are chances that there may be any other factor(s) that influences impulsive buying other than mentioned in the questions.
- The study is only customer based. It completely ignores the marketers or sellers' efforts to attract the customers and result into impulsive buying.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This deals with description of methodology and the steps taken for collection and organization of data and presenting the findings of investigation. The methodology of research indicates the general pattern of organizing the procedures for gathering valid and reliable data or the purpose of investigation (KOTHORI,1996). The methodology of the study includes the description of research design, population, sampling technique, data collection procedures and methods of analysis.

QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

The data has been gathered through structured questionnaire, which has been designed on the basis on the purpose of this study.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE

The target populations were women aged between 18-25 years.

EXTENT AND SAMPLE

The study was conducted among women studying in college. For this study it was relevant to obtain a sample of about 100 respondents all them were women. All of them are between 18-25 years of age.

DATA COLLECTION

The method used for data collection was structured questionnaire. There are 13 questions. The questions are based on the age the income level or the monthly allowances, marital status. The questionnaires were thoroughly checked and edited.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

QUESTION 1: AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS:

Through the questionnaire we can conclude that most of the respondents belong to the age group of 20-25 years of age. The minimum age of the respondents is 20 years while the maximum is 25 years. Age contributes as one of the major factor for influencing the buying behavior.

QUESTION 2: MONTHLY ALLOWANCE:

The respondents had been asked about their monthly allowances. As the survey was conducted in a college, most of them are not earning. About 55% of respondents say that their allowance monthly is below Rs5000. Monthly salary or incomes or allowances directly affects the buying pattern or the impulsive buying behavior of the people.

QUESTION 3: HOW OFTEN DO YOU SHOP? (ANYTHING RANGING FROM CLOTHES TO FOOD ITEMS):

It is important to understand how often a person shops. Here majority of people have mentioned that they shop once or twice a week.

QUESTION 4: DO YOU BUY SOMETHING ON THE SPUR OF THE MOMENT? (ANYTHING RANGING FROM CLOTHES TO FOOD ITEMS):

About 75% of respondents have agreed that they do buy something on the spur of the moment. Followed by 15% how say that yes they do and 8% who do not. Buying on the spur of the moment without planning itself serves as impulsive buying.

QUESTION 5: WHAT PUSHES YOU TO BUY THINGS?

Here, most of the respondents (53%) have agreed that they buy things according to their need which is opposite of impulsive buying. The rest 20% agree to attractive prices which is one of the major causes of impulsive buying and the rest 26% say its according to any offers on the product.

QUESTION 6: HAVE YOU EVER CONTINUED TO BUY PRODUCTS IN SPITE OF THE FINANCIAL AND FAMILY PROBLEMS YOUR PURCHASE CAUSED?

About 53% of the respondents have agreed that they sometimes have bought products or have continued buying products in spite of financial or family problems their purchase caused. This means that they are more likely to go for impulsive buying.

QUESTION 7: CAREFUL PLANNING OF PURCHASES:

About 55% of the respondents have agreed that they carefully plan their purchases while among the remaining 37 % and 6% admit they sometimes do and they never respectively.

QUESTION 8: I BUY THINGS ACCORDING TO HOW I FEEL AT THE MOMENT (ANYTHING RANGING FROM FOODS TO CLOTHES):

About 51% of the respondent have clearly mentioned that they buy things according to their mood or how they feel at that time or the moment. While 42% say they sometimes which may also mean they are into impulsive buying.

QUESTION 9: "BUY NOW THINK LATER" DESCRIBES ME:

About 48% of the respondents have agreed that “buy now think later” describes them these many people are more likely to buy things anytime of the moment while 8 % agree to it and the remaining say never.

QUESTION 10: I HAVE OFTEN BOUGHT A PRODUCT THAT I DO NOT NEED

About 8% of the people gave agreed that they often buy products that do not need while 55% think sometimes they do and the rest 35% says never.

QUESTION 11: I HAVE OFTEN BOUGHT PRODUCTS BECAUSE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT OR BECAUSE MY FRIENDS HAVE IT:

About 40% of the people believe that they sometimes they buy products because of celebrity endorsements or because their friends have it. This shows that it is one of the important factors for impulsive buying while 53% say no and the remaining have agreed on it.

QUESTION 12: DO YOU SHOP TO KILL YOUR LEISURE TIME:

About 35% of people have agreed that sometimes they do shop to kill their leisure time while 57% have said no and the remaining 6% have said yes.

QUESTION 13: Are you aware of impulsive buying while shopping?

About 80% of the respondents have agreed that they are aware of impulsive buying while the rest 20% agree that they do not. Lack of awareness can also lead to impulsive buying.

FINDINGS

- In the analysis, it is seen that most of the students have the knowledge of what is impulse buying, while there are still quite a number of students who are not aware of impulse buying behavior.
- More number of the students are seen to be having 5000 or less than 5000 monthly allowance as they are not yet working and the rest are seen to be having more than 5000 monthly allowances.
- To analyze the shopping pattern, it can be seen that a larger proportion of the students shop once or twice a month, while a reasonable lot of students shopping more than twice a month followed by a few numbers of students shopping once almost every day.
- More than half of the students agree to be shopping sometimes or rarely in the spur of the moment while, a smaller number of students responded positively towards buying impulsively almost every time they shop.
- Among all the respondents, most of them responded positively towards impulse buying because of the need of the product. Whereas, a similar number of students responded equally towards impulse buying because of attractive prices and discounts and offers.
- A considerable number of students have agreed to buying impulsively sometimes even if though they have financial problems while a smaller number of students disagreed to it.

- Most of the students responded positively towards buying things according to their mood and how they feel at the time of buying without considering the prices and offers. While, others responded negatively towards buying according to their moods which can be concluded as the latter lot is more into impulsive buying than the former.
- The chart shows considerably similar lot of students agreeing to have been buying now and think later as well as others disagreeing to the fact of buying now and think later.
- Most of the responses for things bought that they do not need are positive while there are students who responded negatively towards buying things that they do not need.
- A considerable number of students responded positively towards shopping to kill their leisure time, while, a majority of the students responded against it.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study of the impulse buying behavior in young women, it can be seen that women intend to shop in the spur of the moment if they get special offers and discounts. Impulse buying is usually seen with the small things like every day essentials that are kept near the billing counter that the customers pickup impulsively while billing all of the other planned products. Here, in the study we can see that many of the students prefer buying products even if they are having financial issues, this shows that impulse buying might also lead to financial break downs among the youngsters as they tend to buy more in order to go with the trend. Creating awareness about the negative impacts of impulse buying specially among the young adults is very important in order to make them plan their expenses accordingly.

DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

The research carried on could be further analyzed in the future for research purposes by other researchers and marketers through a marketer's point of view in order to understand the challenges that they often face in the marketing of a product and the ways that they follow in order to gain the attention of the customers and provide them products with reasonable pricing.

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